

The effects of HRM practices on teamwork and career growth in offshore outsourcing firms

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The Effects of HRM Practices on Teamwork and Career Growth in Offshore Outsourcing Firms

Brief abstract

A study of virtual team members in 14 IT outsourcing firms in Sri Lanka sheds light on the need to balance employee and organizational expectations in settings where hierarchical advancement is limited.

Long abstract

Balancing the short-term goals of the organization with employees' long-term development is of particular interest to the leaders of offshore outsourcing firms. To better understand this challenge, researchers surveyed 170 virtual team members in 14 IT outsourcing firms in Sri Lanka about the impact of their employers' human resource management (HRM) practices on their performance and career growth. The findings reveal the importance of performance management, capability development, and the integration of various HRM practices in fostering both the teamwork that is crucial to attain business objectives, as well as the professional development essential to meeting employees' expectations regarding their career growth.

Traditional careers that offer lifetime job security to those who climb the organizational ladder while receiving increases in status and income in exchange for their hard work and loyalty are no longer the norm. Widespread downsizing and organizational restructuring are among the reasons for the shift to alternative career paths (Reitman & Schneer, 2008). Today's workplaces are focused on continuous development and psychological success rather than on vertical advancement and job security (Lips-Wiersma & Hall, 2007; Sullivan & Arthur, 2006).

In such a business environment, managing employees who work in virtual teams, such as those in the offshore information technology (IT) outsourcing sector, can be particularly challenging (Mishra & Mahanty, 2014; Saxena & Burmann, 2014). Employees no longer identify with a single organization, and lateral job mobility is common (Wickramasinghe, 2016; Wickramasinghe & Nandula, 2015). Since work that is performed offshore demands coordination with team members in various time zones around the world, these employees are expected to always be available to the organization, even outside official work hours (Scholarios & Marks, 2004). And technological

advancements in information and communication technology (ICT) make 24/7 access to these workers possible. Employees in this sector do not follow the standard career trajectory characterized by stable and linear growth in a single organization under the employer's direct supervision (Baruch, 2006). In such a setting, the links between an organization and its employees are less structured and less permanent (Sullivan & Arthur, 2006).

Although today's employees are expected to take more responsibility in managing their own careers, their employer's responsibility in helping them achieve a more fulfilling quality of life while on the job cannot be ignored (Savickas, 2011). Employees' self-directed career management initiatives tend to be driven by personal aspirations rather than organizational needs (Reitman & Schmeer, 2008). As a result, when employees experience a lack of career growth opportunities within a particular firm, they tend to look for better opportunities elsewhere (Wang, Weng, McElroy, Ashkanasy, & Lievens, 2014). Indeed, organizations may find it difficult to recruit, manage, and retain employees unless they provide an environment that will offer employees enough opportunities so that they are not tempted to leave (Reitman & Schmeer, 2008). In the current environment, it is vital for business leaders to adopt practices that balance employees' need for career growth and their organization's need for committed performance (Wang et al., 2014).

To better understand the nature of the employee-employer relationship in this new context, researchers polled 170 virtual team members in 14 offshore IT outsourcing firms in Sri Lanka about the impact of their employers' human resource management (HRM) practices on their career growth and performance.

A Review of the Virtual Team Context

In a globalized business environment, tasks often need to be quickly handled by experts who are geographically dispersed. Advances in ICT have helped facilitate the coordination of work across time and space. It is now common for businesses in various industries in the West to contract out their front- and back-office work to organizations located in Asia, Russia, Eastern Europe, and Latin America, where labor costs are low and the talent pool is deep. These factors have led to the creation of virtual teams to perform offshore outsourced work (Mishra & Mahanty, 2014; Saxena & Burmann, 2014).

The term "virtual team" is used to refer to a temporary network of employees who, though organizationally or geographically dispersed, collaborate on specific tasks while communicating via ICT. "Temporary" means that team members may not share a past job history and may not have

opportunities to work together in the future (Reed & Knight, 2010). When distances between team members are great, the term “global virtual team” may be used (Anh, Cruzes, & Conradi, 2012).

Regardless of the advantages of virtual teams, organizational leaders may encounter difficulties in bringing together the team members needed to achieve their objectives (Anh et al., 2012; Foss, Minbaeva, Pedersen, & Reinholt, 2009). The main advantage of virtual teams is their flexibility: Their temporary lifespan allows for rapid formation and disbandment. Yet, this characteristic can also hinder cooperation among team members, hampering a team’s performance (Garrison, Wakefield, Xu, & Kim, 2010). A review of previous research suggests that while organizational leaders expect virtual teamwork to result in various psychosocial outcomes, the team members themselves may be primarily concerned with their own career growth.

A Focus on Team Psychosocial Outcomes

The success of a particular task can be interpreted in terms of task outcomes and perceived psychosocial outcomes. In outsourcing work, task outcomes include adherence to timelines, budget, and quality, while perceived psychosocial outcomes include team members’ evaluation of experienced friendliness, support, the enjoyment of participation in the team, and the level of team interactions (Pinto & Pinto, 1990). Team members typically have more control over team psychosocial outcomes than they do task outcomes (Andres, 2002).

Over the years, the proxies used to evaluate team psychosocial outcomes have been widened. For instance, Hertel et al. (2005) showed the importance of initiative within the team, team efficiency, and overall team effectiveness as dimensions of team psychosocial outcomes. Staples and Webster (2007) identified the importance of team members’ perceptions toward their intention to remain on the team, ability to cope in the team context, and satisfaction with the team. Bourgault, Drouin, and Hamel (2008) identified the need to evaluate team members’ perception toward holding team meetings, setting common objectives, planning and organizing team tasks, and creating and maintaining a good teamwork environment. Wickramasinghe (2016) showed the importance of experienced friendliness and support, ability to cope, recognition of individual team members, solidarity, participative decision-making, and tolerance of new ideas within the team as psychosocial outcomes in the context of offshore IT outsourcing.

A View to Career Growth

The traditional considerations of individuals' career growth in terms of hierarchical progression and job security have become less attractive with the globalization of business operations and widespread organizational restructuring (Reitman & Schneer, 2008; Wang et al., 2014). The proxies used to assess career growth have widened to incorporate such dimensions as challenging work, travel, flexibility, contribution, and autonomy. For instance, Jans (1989) proposed to capture individuals' career growth by evaluating their perceptions of the chances of development within their organizations. Weer (2006) defined career growth as an individual's perception of beneficial career development experiences. Weng, McElroy, Morrow, and Liu (2010) identified the degree to which a job enables an individual to develop skills and knowledge as an important dimension of career growth. Therefore, focus on organizational career growth provides a better understanding of one's career-related experiences, and of whether the employing organization creates an environment for employees to meet their career-related expectations.

While it is to be expected that employees' experiences of career growth are associated with employee-friendly organizational policies, such as skill development, research shows that employees' experience of career growth within their employing organizations may also influence their total well-being, and even future career prospects outside the current organization (McElroy & Weng, 2016).

Addressing the Impact of HRM Practices

Acemoglu and Pischke (1998) and Morissette (1993) suggest that in a non-homogeneous labor market, in which skills, education, and training vary, enterprises seek to make the most of their employees' capabilities. While providing employees with financial and nonfinancial rewards based on productivity and profits, firms manage employees' careers and obtain advantages from the capabilities that employees develop overtime. In uncertain business environments, organizations tend to place a premium on immediate returns from human resources. In such circumstances, business leaders may strategically choose HRM practices that maximize firm performance and profits (Dickson, Weaver, & Hoy, 2006). When firms maintain policies that enable employees to fulfil their career expectations within the organization, they reduce the likelihood that employees will leave for better prospects elsewhere.

There are numerous HRM practices that organizations can adopt to remain sustainable and competitive while developing their employees' careers (Tocher & Rutherford, 2009). Proper selection and execution of HRM practices may enhance and reinforce employees' commitment to their tasks and on-the-job performance. At the same time, when workplace practices strategically

address employees' career needs, employees tend to develop favorable attitudes toward organizational career growth within the organization.

In the context of offshore outsourcing, however, various studies have shown that opportunities for employees to achieve hierarchical advancement are very limited (Gorjup, Valverde, & Ryan, 2008; Wickramasinghe, 2009; Wickramasinghe & Jayaweera, 2010). Other studies have found that firms provide skill development opportunities to satisfy both employees' needs for career growth and organizations' needs for short-term productivity (Heilmann, 2011; Wickramasinghe, 2009; Wickramasinghe & Liyanage, 2013). In some instances, employees self-initiate career management strategies to stay focused on their careers and career development, even if their employers do not provide them with skill- development opportunities (Wickramasinghe & Jayaweera, 2011).

Even firms espousing a short-term productivity focus in outsourcing may apply certain HRM practices to not only ensure sustainability, but also to foster employees' favorable perceptions of the work environment as satisfying their need for growth (Wickramasinghe & Liyanage, 2013; Wickramasinghe & Nisaf, 2013). Further, although HRM practices associated with hierarchical advancement are rare in offshore outsourcing, HRM practices associated with expertise development, professional identity creation, and challenging work are not scarce (Wickramasinghe & Liyanage, 2013). The motivation for offering these practices could stem from competitive pressures in the offshore outsourcing sector and from a recognition of the organizations' reliance on the capabilities of their employees as a source of competitive advantage. Accordingly, employees attached to virtual teams need to be effectively managed to ensure the attainment of performance targets. This line of reasoning leads to two questions:

- Do an organization's performance management and human resource development (HRD) practices influence employees' perceptions of career growth?
- Do the performance management and HRD practices that employees experience influence the way they coordinate virtual teamwork in an offshore outsourcing context?

An analysis of the impact of performance management and HRD in settings where hierarchical advancement is limited could yield valuable information for future research and policy making.

Performance Management

Performance management is a continuous process of identifying, measuring, and improving the performance of target individuals and units with the ultimate intention of achieving strategic organizational objectives (Abu-Doleh & Weir, 2007; DeNisi, 2011). The success of performance

management depends on the active involvement of both employees and their supervisors in setting performance goals, reviewing results, and rewarding performance (Biron, Farndale, & Paauwe, 2011). The value of performance management as a mechanism for managerial decision-making depends on the capability of the system to provide accurate and timely information on performance (Cook & Crossman, 2004). When such systems do not effectively managing performance, there can be negative consequences. Employees' confidence in and satisfaction with the system may drop, performance at both the individual and organizational level may not measure up to expectations, and the credibility of the entire HRM system can be damaged, leading to tension between employees and the leaders of the organization (Wickramasinghe & Samaratunga, 2016). Ideally, a performance management system should ensure the creation of a work environment that meets organizational and individual needs.

As a vital piece of any HRM system, performance management serves strategic and tactical purposes (Armstrong & Taylor, 2014; Biron et al., 2011). Strategically speaking, performance management provides valuable information that links corporate and individual goals. This involves evaluating individuals' performance against pre-set standards and reinforcing individual and unit behaviour that is consistent with corporate-level objectives (Abu-Doleh & Weir, 2007; Biron et al., 2011). Armstrong and Taylor (2014) identified this linking of corporate and individual goals as vertical integration – the alignment of business, team, and individual performance goals.

In terms of tactical goals, performance management provides valuable information for coherent decision-making regarding HR development and management (Biron et al., 2011). These decisions address such issues as the identification of performance deficiencies and training needs, the provision of feedback, and the determination of rewards. Armstrong and Taylor (2014) identified this integrated decision-making as horizontal integration.

When employees are aware of the use of performance management data to make critical decisions regarding rewards, skill development, and career management, they realize that the organization values them (Biron et al., 2011). Formalized job-based performance evaluation with opportunities for two-way communication guides individuals to achieve a higher level of performance, enhancing their motivation (Wickramasinghe & Liyanage, 2013). According to Cleveland and Murphy (1992), individuals are most interested in performance management that addresses task-performance, interpersonal, and internalized goals; the creation of a positive work climate; how to increase one's standing in the organization; and the maintenance of values. Further, research has identified the accomplishment of task goals to be influenced by the level of achievements in interpersonal goals,

such as maintaining a positive work group climate (Cleveland & Murphy, 1992). Therefore, performance management that enables employees to use their skills and talents to pursue what they view as worthwhile goals ultimately has a significant impact on their level of happiness (Wickramasinghe & Perera, 2012). Thus, it is hypothesized that:

H1: Performance management practices lead to the achievement of team members' interpersonal goals.

H2: Performance management practices lead to employees' career growth.

Human Resource Development

Effective human resource development practices increase the chances for an organization to achieve its objectives by ensuring employee commitment (Castellanos & Martín, 2011). They also provide employees with structure, direction, meaning, and purpose while fulfilling their needs for personal development (Adamson, Doherty, & Viney, 1998). Organizations in new business sectors like outsourcing have recognized that having a formalized approach to managing people is a valuable asset in a knowledge economy, for it helps define firm-level strategic capabilities, develop and manage employees by leveraging the knowing-learning-doing nexus, create knowledge as an organizational and individual asset, and minimize the risk associated with the loss of requisite capabilities (Whicker & Andrews, 2004).

Previous research provides ample evidence of the use of HRD with a short-term focus in IT outsourcing. For example, Wickramasinghe and Widyaratne (2012) note the identification of training needs through daily and weekly meetings that project teams conduct to handle problems on the job. Such programs, however, are primarily intended to enhance productivity and upgrade skills in order to complete projects at hand rather than to address long-term improvements for either the firm or its employees (Wickramasinghe, 2009; Wickramasinghe & Liyanage, 2013). In these cases, widely used HRD programs focused on on-the-job training through additional job-related responsibilities, feedback from superiors, self-study, learning blogs, and customized training provided by vendors on specific project-related topics (Wickramasinghe & Jayaweera, 2010; Wickramasinghe & Kumara, 2009; Wickramasinghe & Weliwitigoda, 2011). Relying on employees' tacit knowledge, firms were found to mainly promote "communities of practice" among them (Abeysekera, 2007). No exception was made even for managerial level employees. Job rotation, mentoring, action learning, coaching, learning logs, diaries, and guided reflection were rarely used.

There has been an increase in the use of e-learning solutions — such as online databases, videos, Web-based HTML files, social networking and bookmarking, and Wikis — to improve employees' procedural, administrative, and job-related technical knowledge and skills (Wickramasinghe, 2011; Wickramasinghe & Nisaf, 2013; Wickramasinghe & Widyaratne, 2012). When organizations provide such skill-development opportunities, it is important to ensure that they align with employees' career goals (Wang et al.,2014; Nouri & Parker,2013). Given the research reviewed above, it is hypothesized that:

H3: HRD practices lead to the achievement of team members' interpersonal goals.

H2: HRD practices lead to employees' career growth.

A Look at Virtual Teamwork in Sri Lanka

For the purposes of this study, a virtual team was defined as a network of dispersed group of people who temporarily work together toward a common goal and share resources, know-how, services, and by-products. Researchers identified 14 offshore IT outsourcing firms in Sri Lanka that use virtual teams to achieve job tasks and surveyed a random sample of employees from these firms who worked on a virtual team for at least one year. No more than 5 percent of employees were selected from the same team. To facilitate data collection, a contact person was identified at each firm. A self-administered survey questionnaire was pre-tested with a random sample that fit the intended sample of the study prior to distribution. The anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension. Of the total number of 250 questionnaires distributed, 170 responses were received, yielding a response rate of 68 percent.

Of the respondents, 53 percent were female and 47 percent were male. All had a bachelor's degree as the highest level of qualification (equating to level 5 on the Sri Lanka Qualification Framework [SLQF]), thus meeting the minimum entry qualification in the sector. A majority, 54 percent, reported that they supervise subordinates; the remaining said they do not have supervisory responsibilities. The mean age of respondents was 29 years. They had an average of three years of work experience with the current employer, with an average one-and-a-half years of experience in their current position. On average, three staff members handled HRM matters at the respondents' firms.

The researchers used 11 items to measure the HRM practices experienced by employees in the study. Those measures and the results of factor analysis are shown in **Exhibit 1** and **Exhibit 2**. The researchers used 10 items to measure experienced outcomes. Those item measures and the results

of factor analysis are given in **Exhibit 3** and **Exhibit 4**. Respondents were asked to rate each of these items were on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree).

In addition, the researchers collected data on three individual demographic variables and five firm characteristics as controls. The individual characteristics were age (in years), tenure (in years), and the supervision of subordinates (no = 0, yes = 1). The popularity of the firm in the business sector and its stability in the business sector were measured using single items for each, assessed on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree). Further, the number of staff involved in handling the HRM matters was also controlled, as shown in **Exhibit 5**.

[Exhibits 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 about here.]

Harman's single-factor test was conducted to assess common method variance. Neither a single factor nor a general factor emerged from this analysis that could account for the majority of variance, which fulfilled recommended guidelines (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee & Podsakoff, 2003). For all main constructs, recommended statistical tests were conducted to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias. In doing so, the researchers tested the data for appropriate internal consistency reliability, factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity, and construct reliability, following recommended guidelines and statistical thresholds (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham (2006). The variables demonstrated good internal consistency reliability, factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity, and construct reliability. Regression analysis was used for hypotheses testing.

Results Highlight the Impact of HRM Practices

As shown in Exhibit 1, the availability of skill development programs obtained the highest mean value (mean = 3.65, SD = .80), followed by the fulfilment of immediate skill requirements to perform job tasks (mean = 3.42, SD = .72).

The responses for the 11 measures of HRM practices had a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.892. Principal component factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 73 percent (73.20) of the variance. The items, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Exhibit 2. Factor 1 was labeled as "performance management," factor 2 as "capability development," and factor 3 as "integration of practices." The result suggests that the integration of HRM practices can be identified as a separate factor.

Means and standard deviations for expected outcomes are shown in Exhibit 3. Item 1 regarding satisfaction with the mutual support among team members obtained the highest mean value (mean = 4.15, SD = .55), followed by satisfaction with the coordination within the team (mean = 3.99, SD = .67).

The responses for the 10-item measure of expected outcomes had a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.857. Principal component factor analysis yielded a set of two factors, which explained 69(68.91) percent of the variance. The items, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Exhibit 4. Factor 1 was labeled as "professional development" and Factor 2 as "team interpersonal goals." The means, standard deviations, and zero-order correlations for the study variables are shown in Exhibit 5.

Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses concerning whether the HRM practices experienced by employees influence their perceptions of career growth and the way they coordinate teamwork in the offshore outsourcing context. As **Exhibit 6** shows, control variables of tenure in the present workplace, tenure in the present job in the present workplace, the supervision of subordinates, the number of staff members handling human resource matters, and the stability of the firm are significant in predicting individuals' experience of professional development in the organization (Adj. $R^2 = .255$, $p < 0.001$). These control variables are not significant, however, in predicting team interpersonal goals (Adj. $R^2 = .063$, $p > 0.05$).

[Exhibit 6 about here.]

With regard to the effect of HRM practices on professional development, the adjusted R^2 of 0.484 reveals that the final model explained 48 percent of the variance in professional development ($p < 0.001$). The inclusion of three main independent variables of performance management, capability development, and the integration of practices into the model resulted in 23 percent of the variance being explained (R^2 Change = 0.228, $p < 0.001$). That is, these three variables alone explained 23 percent of the variability of professional development. As can be seen in Exhibit 6, the individual effects of all three factors were also significant. Overall, the results of the regression analysis provide evidence that performance management, capability development, and the

integration of practices play a significant role in employees' perceptions of professional development. This supports H1 and H3.

With regard to the effect of HRM practices on team interpersonal goals, the adjusted R^2 of 0.193 reveals that the final model explained 19 percent of the variance in achieving team interpersonal goals ($p < 0.001$). The inclusion of the three main independent variables of performance management, capability development, and the integration of practices into the model resulted in 14 percent of the variance being explained (R^2 Change = 0.139, $p < 0.001$). That is, these three variables alone explained 14 percent of the variability of team interpersonal goals. As can be seen in Exhibit 6, the individual effects of all three factors were also significant. Overall, the results of the regression analysis provide evidence that performance management, capability development, and the integration of practices play a significant role in employees' perceptions of achieving team interpersonal goals. This supports H2 and H4.

Toward the Effective Management of Virtual Teams

Virtual team structures lie at the core of the outsourcing business. Shifting team membership, the temporary lifespan of virtual teams, and the varying expectations, perspectives, and skills of the individual members can make it difficult to coordinate interdependent tasks in virtual team settings to achieve a common purpose. How these challenges are addressed ultimately can determine whether the team succeeds in reaching its goals. As this study found, the appropriate adoption of HRM practices of performance management and HRD helps fulfil the needs of both employees and their organizations. The study also highlighted the value of integrating HRM practices. These findings have both theoretical and practical implications. Academics and practitioners need a better understanding of the full context of offshore outsourcing so that they can make informed decisions on the influence of HRM practices on employees in this sector.

The globalization of business operations has led to a significant increase in the offshoring of services to developing countries. The success of such endeavors mainly depends on the costs and capabilities of the offshore location. Meanwhile, the outsourcing sector is predominantly built on short-term financial objectives. As a result, outsourcing firms may not be prepared to invest in a comprehensive set of HRM practices, such as succession planning and career management, that have a long-term focus. Performance management and career management practices investigated in the study had a short-term focus with more emphasis on performance appraisal and HRD. This suggests that the global competitive environment could have affected outsourcing firms' preferred HRM practices. This situation is not limited to the outsourcing sector, however; such an orientation

was also found in Sri Lanka's export-based manufacturing operations (Mamman, Akuratiyagamage, &Rees, 2006).

Although the firms in the study had an overall short-term focus, the performance management and HRD practices they adopted reflect managements' interest in and commitment to continuous employee development. These practices seem to encourage employees to develop the capabilities they need to perform current job tasks, as well as others in the organization. The provision of these practices, therefore, not only increases the likelihood of successful task completion to fulfill organizational expectations, but also leads employees to perceive opportunities open to them that they consider relevant to and valuable for their professional development in this sector.

The findings also suggest the importance of distinguishing between the application of specific HRM practices and their integration with others. This is clearly visible in the item loadings between performance management (e.g., performance appraisal system provides performance rating procedure for employees at each level), HRD (e.g., the skill development programs of my organization address the immediate skill requirements to perform job tasks), and the integration of practices (e.g., performance appraisal feedback is used to identify short-term skill development needs). Thus, it appears that it is important to adopt practices in an integrated manner instead of implementing stand-alone practices, even in a context where short-term profit and operational requirements dominate.

With regard to the implications for practice, the findings revealed the impact that certain HRM practices have on psychosocial outcomes in an environment requiring teamwork — such as the degree of experienced friendliness, support, and ability to cope — which may ultimately enable team members to meet their performance targets.

Second, the study showed that the HRM practices that an organization adopts can have a positive impact even on individuals in nontraditional careers who are expected to take the lead in their own development. Opportunities for professional development could be useful in one's current position and/or in other positions within or outside the current employing organization.

Since HRM practices are central to the management of any business operation, they can generate valuable information to inform decisions concerning such matters as rewards administration, employee training, performance assessment, and documentation, particularly when they are integrated. Overall, the study pointed up the importance of HRM practices in outsourcing as not

only a way of achieving organizational interests, but also as a way of influencing employees' expectations.

Although the original goal was to investigate abroad spectrum of HRM practices, the researchers had to limit their investigation because of the short-term focus of the practices adopted by the firms in the study. Nonetheless, the findings offer valuable insight and signal the need for more research in this area.

First, future research could investigate the impact of specific HRD programs on firm-level outcomes and employees' preferences regarding career advancement in the offshore outsourcing environment. Second, when taking into account the short-term focus of skill development, firms as well as employees could benefit from a study of the fit between employees' professional development goals and the opportunities for skill development that the organization offers. Future research could look into how individuals' career goals could be transformed in an era of nontraditional careers and the means of achieving such a fit for the benefit of both employees and employers. Finally, additional research could investigate whether professional development helps reduce turnover among employees. Such studies may yield valuable insights to further guide business leaders on how best to ensure the success and sustainability of their offshore outsourcing operations.

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Exhibit 1. Means and Standard Deviations: HRM Practices

	Mean	S.D.
1. Variety of skill development programs are available in my organization	3.65	.80
2. Skill development programs address the immediate skill requirements to perform job tasks	3.42	.72
3. Performance appraisal system communicates performance goals at the beginning of the evaluation period	3.40	.83
4. Financial rewards are determined based on performance ratings	3.39	.96
5. Skill development programs are up-to-date by addressing changing industry needs	3.37	.75
6. Performance appraisal system provides performance rating procedure for employees at each level	3.32	.85
7. My performance goals are aligned with departmental/unit goals	3.32	.75
8. My performance goals for the evaluation period are mutually agreed upon in advance with supervisors	3.31	.82
9. Performance appraisal feedback is used to identify short-term skill development needs	3.28	.82
10. We make self-evaluation of our performance as part of the performance management process	3.26	.91
11. Hierarchical movement within my organization is determined based on performance ratings	3.16	.76

Exhibit 2. Factor Analysis: HRM Practices

	F1: Performance management	F2: Capability development	F3: Integration of practices
1. My performance goals are aligned with departmental/unit goals	.867		
2. My performance goals for the evaluation period are mutually agreed upon in advance with supervisors	.853		
3. Performance appraisal system provides performance rating procedure for employees at each level	.813		
4. We make self-evaluation of our performance as part of the performance management process	.788		
5. Performance appraisal system communicates performance goals at the beginning of the evaluation period	.704		
6. Variety of skill development programs are available in my organization		.849	
7. Skill development program are up-to-date by addressing changing industry needs		.805	
8. Skill development program address the immediate skill requirements to perform job tasks		.730	
9. Performance appraisal feedback is used to identify short-term skill development needs			.807
10. Financial rewards are determined based on performance ratings			.722
11. Hierarchical movement within my organization is determined based on performance ratings			.701
Explained variation	39.08	19.16	14.96
Cronbach's alpha	.909	.820	.716
AVE	.65	.63	.55
Construct reliability	.90	.84	.79

Exhibit 3. Means and Standard Deviations: Experienced Outcomes

	Mean	S.D.
1. I am satisfied with the mutual support among members in the team	4.15	.55
2. I am satisfied with the coordination within the team	3.99	.67
3. I am satisfied with the amenability among members to maintain the team	3.89	.76
4. I am satisfied with the opportunities received to assume various job related responsibilities	3.59	.86
5. I am satisfied with the opportunities received to accumulate job related experience	3.51	.81
6. I am satisfied with the confident I gained in my job role to take-up future responsibilities	3.50	.87
7. I am satisfied with the opportunities received to gain job related skills	3.46	.95
8. I am satisfied with the contribution made by individual members in the team	3.45	.94
9. I am satisfied with the opportunities received for my personal development	3.43	.98
10. I am satisfied with the improvements in my outlook due to job-specific exposure received from my organization	3.35	.96

Exhibit 4. Factor Analysis: Experienced Outcomes

	F1: Professional development	F2: Team interpersonal goals
1. I am satisfied with the improvements in my outlook due to job-specific exposure received from my organization	.847	
2. I am satisfied with the opportunities received to gain job related skills	.829	
3. I am satisfied with the opportunities received for my personal development	.819	
4. I am satisfied with the confident I gained in my job role to take-up future responsibilities	.803	
5. I am satisfied with the opportunities received to accumulate job related experience	.763	
6. I am satisfied with the opportunities received to assume various job related responsibilities	.735	
7. I am satisfied with the coordination within the team		.792
8. I am satisfied with the amenability among members to maintain the team		.777
9. I am satisfied with the mutual support among members in the team		.765
10. I am satisfied with the contribution made by individual members in the team		.736
Explained variation	40.00	28.91
Cronbach's alpha	.911	.815
AVE	.64	.59
Construct reliability	.91	.85

Exhibit 5. Correlations for the Study Variables

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1. Firm tenure	3.0	1.7	-											
2. Job tenure	1.5	1.2	.433**	-										
3. Age	29	2.0	.546**	.300**	-									
4. Supervision of subordinates ^a	-	-	.291**	.050	.460**	-								
5. No. of staff handling HR	3.0	2.0	.142	.163	.048	.096	-							
6. Popularity of the firm	4.48	.55	.150	.029	.039	.070	.188*	-						
7. Stability of the firm	4.19	.68	.166	.066	.077	.081	.116	.469**	-					
8. Performance management	3.32	.72	.128	.080	.125	.031	.120	.159*	.258**	.81				
9. Capability development	3.49	.65	.084	.113	.152	.130	.193*	.246**	.269**	.319**	.79			
10. Integration of practices	3.27	.69	.164	.129	.030	.115	.253**	.140	.278**	.395**	.397**	.74		
11. Professional development Team	3.46	.76	.194	.173	.009	.245**	.249**	.104	.212**	.315**	.379**	.358**	.80	
12. interpersonal goals	3.87	.60	.104	.104	.072	.062	.097	.226**	.203**	.358**	.331**	.351**	.233**	.77

Notes: * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$; diagonal entries, square root of AVE; off-diagonal entries, correlations between constructs; ^a Binary-coded variables.

Exhibit 6. Regression Results

Step	Variable	Professional development					Team interpersonal goals				
		β	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics			β	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics		
				R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change			R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change
1	Firm tenure	.274**	.255***	.287	9.13	.000	.040	.063	.103	2.61	.014
	Job tenure	.238**					.053				
	Age	.093					.025				
	Supervision of subordinates	.236**					.044				
	No. of staff handling HR	.177*					.059				
	Popularity of the firm	.034					.115				
	Stability of the firm	.212**					.106				
2	Firm tenure	.160*	.484***	.228	24.47	.000	.057	.193	.139	9.54	.000
	Job tenure	.218*					.026				
	Age	.043					.031				
	Supervision of subordinates	.213**					.052				
	No. of staff handling HR	.069					.006				
	Popularity of the firm	.015					.122				
	Stability of the firm	.049					.061				
	Performance management	.340***					.290**				
	Capability development	.436***					.156*				
	Integration of practices	.490***					.247**				

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$